

MECHANISMS OF STRAIN INDUCED ALIGNMENT OF CARBON NANOTUBES (CNT): PROCESS SCALE-UP AND QUASI-CONTINUOUS HIGHLY ALIGNED CNT MATERIAL

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1. Introduction

Random carbon nanotube (CNT) networks have shown unique property improvement when uniaxial strains are applied. A high degree of alignment can be induced on the CNT networks by plastic deformation. This modification leads to substantial improvements in properties such as tensile strength and Young's modulus along the alignment direction. The alignment process is also scalable, which makes the highly aligned CNT materials via strain-induced alignment an attractive material for use in a wide variety of industrial applications. The high degree of alignment is achieved due to the extra high CNT aspect ratio that causes high degrees of entanglement and locking points between the CNTs. In this research, the changes in both microscopic and macroscopic morphology of the CNT networks were studied and the mechanisms of performance enhancement were investigated. The high degree of CNT alignment and feasibility for the scaling up of production were demonstrated.

2. Motivation and Materials Selection

CNTs have great potential because of their high mechanical [1-5], electrical [4-6] and thermal [7] properties. The tensile strength for an individual multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) is measured between 11 and 63 GPa [1-4]. However, when the CNT network is fabricated, the theoretical strength of the individual nanotubes is not transferrable because of the lack of alignment and anisotropy within the networks. Many research groups have attempted different techniques to align CNT networks. Of the many methods attempted, mechanical stretching shows promise because of the ability for the process to be scaled up as opposed to the other methods that only produce very small

samples. In order to make breakthroughs in this process, analysing and understanding how the CNT networks are microscopically and macroscopically modified during the different stages of uniaxial strain applied during stretching is critical. A crucial feature of the random CNT network needs to possess is an extremely high aspect ratio for each constituent CNT. The aspect ratio for MWNTs is roughly 100,000 (length of ~1 mm and diameter of ~3-8 nm) and can withstand large stretching strains. Such ultra-high aspect ratio allows for the macroscopic network to be stretchable and achieve high degree of alignment. The randomly dispersed MWNT sheets discussed in this paper were provided by Nanocomp Technologies, Inc. (Concord, NH). The sheets are highly stretchable due to their extra-large aspect ratio, high nanotube waviness and entanglements, as well as their unique catalyst physical locking points from the manufacturing process, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Ductile network of randomly oriented high aspect ratio MWNTs with heavy entanglement.

Raman scattering techniques were used to investigate the orientation and structural changes when CNT sheets were plastically deformed to different levels of strain. Tensile tests during and after stretching as well as Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) imaging were also used to characterize the network structures and properties at different levels of plastic deformation.

3. Experimentation

Sheets of MWNT have shown the capability to be plastically elongated consistently to 30% strain without damaging the CNTs or the network. The use of CNT networks in the absence of significant levels of added polymers or other matrices is crucial for understanding the nanoscale mechanisms of plastic deformation. It is important to clearly observe nanotube to nanotube interactions during strain application to reveal the load transfer mechanisms within the networks.

The sheets of random MWNTs from Nanocomp Technologies were cut into samples with a 1:5 aspect ratio, and then placed on a universal tester AGS-J (Shimadzu Scientific Inc., Japan). A constant head displacement rate was set at 0.5 mm/min. The low strain rate was chosen to reduce the impulse loads applied on the nodes of the carbon nanotube network and prevent premature failure of the sample. The elongation or strain was monitored and the machine was stopped at selected strain levels. To reduce the elastic spring back of the network, the sample was held on the machine until the uniaxial force reduced to a near zero level, and then the sample was removed. Fig. 2 shows the stress-strain dynamics during the strain application process, which was evidenced that the procedure is highly repeatable and consistent.

Fig. 2. Typical tensile stress-strain curves, and sample morphology produced by the MWNT sheets with strains of 10%, 20%, and 30%.

The resulting SEM images in Fig. 3 show the microscale evolution of the CNT networks from random orientation (a) to a densely packed structure, with heavily bundled “ropes” and an improved aligned degree in the horizontal direction (the direction of strain) (d).

Fig. 3. SEM images of MWCNT networks at strains of 0% (a), 10% (b), 20% (c) and 30% (d)

3.2 Comparison with Polymer Stretching

Extensive research has been performed in the field of oriented polymer networks. Cross-linked non-brittle polymer chains show similarity to the

structure of nanotube networks in their nanostructure, morphological changes, and stress/strain characteristics. This study examines the application of brittle-ductility transition fundamentals of polymers to explain the modes and mechanisms of plastic deformation and alignment of the networks.

The nanotube networks' structural evolution and stress-strain behaviours are similar to those of polymer materials [8-10]. Fig. 4 shows the major mechanisms of the brittle and plastic polymers during tensile deformation. The stress-strain dynamic of the bilinear elastic/plastic deformation of the networks is similar to plastic polymers. The difference is that the CNT sheets did not undergo a stress reduction after onset of necking, unlike plastic polymers. This is possibly due to the fibrillar and cross-linked nanostructure of the nanotube network that is slightly more brittle than that of the plastic polymers. The response of the CNT networks can be described as a combination of the cross-linked brittle polymer and the fibrillar plastic polymer stretching behaviours as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. Typical stress-strain curves for the response of a brittle and a plastic polymer to tensile deformation [9-10].

4. Results and discussions

4.1 Interaction Modes during Plastic Deformation

During the stretching, we propose the structural change modes of the nanotube network under tension that are taking place simultaneously within the material. The major modes can be described as

the following: de-bundling, elongation, sliding friction, and self-assembly.

4.1.1 Alignment degree of CNT network with different stretching strains

This mode of the network's deformation during the application of uniaxial strain is individual nanotubes and their bundles undergoing uniaxial stress at each end, and becoming straight and aligned to the elongation direction [6]. Raman measurements of the G-band peak are known to reveal the orientation of the nanotubes [6, 11-12]. Although the Raman measurements are limited to the surface of the material to ~50 nm surface depth (approximately 10-15 nanotube layers), the measurements can be considered representative of strain-induced orientation of the nanotubes throughout the material [11-15]. The polarized Raman spectra was measured first with the polarization parallel to the strain-oriented direction ($\theta = 0^\circ$) then perpendicular to the strain-oriented direction ($\theta = 90^\circ$) and the G-band intensity ratios between the two directions was calculated as shown in Fig. 5. The increase in the alignment degree as the strain increases shows that as the network was plastically deformed, the nanotubes were more aligned and showed a polarized response in direction of alignment.

Fig. 5. Alignment degree calculated from G-band intensity ratios along parallel and perpendicular polarizations to the stretching direction.

4.1.2 Sliding friction mechanism

The sliding friction mode of tension for the CNTs under tensile strain is the axial translation of individual nanotubes and nanotube bundles in close enough proximity to activate physically and chemically induced friction forces. This mode of tension is most prominent at roughly 20% strain as shown in Fig. 6. Here it becomes obvious that nanotubes that were once perpendicular to the axis of orientation are now closer to being oriented parallel to the tensile direction. This change in orientation causes friction between unoriented perpendicular nanotubes and also between co-oriented parallel nanotubes.

Fig. 6. SEM images of MWCNT networks at a 20% strain. Arrows indicate strain direction.

4.1.3 De-bundling mechanism

There is additional tension due to bundles of CNTs either releasing from a bundle or reassembling into another bundle. This is most evident through examining SEM images and estimating bundle size. From Fig. 7, it is clear that the loose bundle in (a) has roughly a diameter of $\sim 1\mu\text{m}$ while the bundle in (b) has a diameter of $\sim 2\mu\text{m}$. This reduction in bundle size is resulted from not only nanotubes being peeled from the bundle but also the nanotubes becoming more intertwined and forming large aligned bundles.

Fig. 7. SEM images of MWCNT bundles at the strains of 20% (a) and 30% (b). Circles indicate bundle size and assembly changes.

4.1.4 Packing and reassembly mechanism

When individual nanotubes and bundles became closer and reassembled into larger bundles to form a denser network, the packing and reassembly of CNTs occurred. The densification of the CNT network decreased void content and activated stronger van der Waals interaction between individual nanotubes, leading to better load transfer. Fig. 7 also shows the extreme densification of the bundles that occurs between 20% and 30% strain. In Fig. 8, it was clearly observed that most ropes formed in the 30% strain sample are larger than the loose ropes in the 10% sample. This formation of the large rope structure is the key to strengthen the

nanostructure by improving load transfer between nanotubes. More than 30% reduction in width at 30% stretching strain also reflects the dense packing as shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Fig. 8. SEM images of MWNT bundles at strains of 10% (a) and 30% (b). Circles indicate CNT ropes that show a different amount of individual nanotubes in large bundles for different strains.

Fig. 9. Width reduction of stretched MWCNT networks with 0%, 10%, 20% and 30% strains.

The shiny surface morphology seen in Fig. 9 illustrates a similar optical phenomenon to the Raman measurements with increasing reflectivity correlated to increasing nanostructure alignment and packing.

4.1.5 Locking points of defects/catalyst

In the MWCNT sheet materials as received, there are significant amounts of defects and residual catalyst nanoparticles. This mode of deformation accounts for the individual nanotubes and nanotube ropes having large deformation due to better load transfer coming from mechanical locking effects of the imperfections during stretching. As seen in Fig. 10, the nanotube bundles in (a) locking with residual catalysts (b) are pulling and entangling with the catalyst nanoparticle. Another important phenomenon is the creation of a locking angle between CNTs. The locking angle was formed by the catalyst intersection points between CNTs when the strain was high and the angle needed for the nanotubes to be parallel cannot be achieved. The dragging tension is also a reason of failure in the networks due to possible stress concentration at the locking points.

Fig.10. SEM images of the MWCNT bundles and defects/catalyst at 20% (a) and 30% (b) strain. Circles indicate defects and residual catalyst nanoparticles.

In order to reveal the effect of alignment on the tensile properties of CNT network, a cycle loading stretching was carried out. Approximate 20% stretching strain was produced for the first cycle, which was followed by two more cycles with about 5% stretching strain.

Fig. 11 shows the stress-strain curves in different cycles. This maximum stress in the prior cycle corresponds to the deformation transition from elastic to plastic deformation on the next cycle. The increase of slope in the elastic portion was caused not only by removing network weak interactions and load transfer, but also microstructure evolution to dense packing and tight bundles along the strain

direction, changing the nanostructure of the material. The tensile strength and modulus increased with the loading cycles.

Fig. 11. Stress-strain curves for a cycle loading stretching of CNT networks, with a 20% stretching strain in the first cycle and 5% stretching strain in the second and third cycles.

4.2 Mechanical Behavior of Stretched CNT Networks

To evaluate the characteristics of the elongated nanotube networks, the Young's modulus and ultimate tensile strength were measured. Samples were cut to ~5mm width with a 20 mm gauge length. Tensile test was conducted on the Shimadzu universal tester with a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min at room temperature. Strain was monitored with a non-contact DVE-201 video extensometer. The thicknesses of the samples were 10-20 μm . Fig. 12 shows the tensile testing curves in the direction of CNT network alignment and Table 1 shows the corresponding Young's modulus and ultimate strength. The samples' pre-test strains were 0%, 10%, 20% and 30% strains.

Randomly oriented buckypaper showed a Young's modulus of 3.12 GPa and a tensile strength of 85.05 MPa. The Young's modulus increased by over 350% and ultimate strength increased by over 160% for the stretched network with 30% strain. It can be seen that the stretch leads to a plastic-elastic transition behavior of the samples with an improved load transfer capacity among densely packed and aligned larger bundles.

Fig. 12. Typical stress-strain curves in the aligned direction for CNT networks with stretching strains of 0%, 10%, 20% and 30%.

	0%	10%	20%	30%
Young's Modulus (Gpa)	3.12	6.47	7.14	10.93
Ultimate Strength (Mpa)	85.05	105.14	125.21	139.92

Table 1. Young's modulus and tensile strength of the CNT networks with 0%, 10%, 20% and 30% stretching strains

5. Process Scaling

A unique feature about the plastic deformation procedure is the ability for the process to be scaled up. Most reported highly aligned CNT fibers and sheets are at the most 20 mm in length which is not a good candidate for traditional carbon fiber manufacturing layups for structural applications. A solution to create large parts of using high aligned CNTs is to use a continuous strain-induced procedure that can be scaled to the large length of CNT networks. Fig. 13 shows the schematic by which the strain is continually induced on the continuous CNT network.

Fig. 13. Quasi-continuous process for stretch alignment of long CNT materials.

6. Conclusions

This research studied the strain-induced deformation and alignment of CNT networks with extra-large CNT aspect ratios. The results show that the plastic deformation is the key to create large deformation and high degree of alignment of CNT networks. The study discussed several deformation mechanisms of CNT networks, compared to polymer brittle-plastic deformation behavior. The approach of strain-induced high degree of alignment of CNT networks has the potential to scale-up to continuous process.

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